

Numerical Study of Tire Lug Angle Configurations to Optimize Traction on Agricultural Terrains

Halidi Ally, Xiulun Wang*, Tingting Wu, Tao Liu, Ge Jun

ABSTRACT

Optimizing traction on agricultural terrains through refined lug angles enhances efficiency, productivity, and cost-effectiveness in farming operations. This study numerically investigates the performance of various tire lug designs across different terrains using advanced simulation techniques. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) with ANSYS is utilized to model tire-soil interactions, while the Improved Tire Model by Wong and Preston-Thomas (ITM-WP) is employed to predict traction performance with a focus on lug angles. The research evaluates five lug designs with angles of 35°, 45°, 55°, 65°, and 75°, incorporating empirical data obtained from laboratory experiments on four types of clayey soil. The findings demonstrate how lug designs influence motion resistance, thrust, and traction, providing practical guidelines for optimizing tire performance. Among the configurations, the 45° lug angle consistently delivers the optimal balance between reduced motion resistance, enhanced thrust, and improved traction, making it the ideal choice for maximizing traction efficiency in clay soils. These insights contribute to the development of more efficient agricultural machinery, reducing soil degradation, improving operational efficiency, and advancing agricultural productivity.

Keywords: *Agricultural Vehicles; ANSYS simulation; Clay soils; Lug angles; Tire-Soil Interaction; Traction Optimization.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural vehicles are essential in modern farming, performing a wide range of tasks from plowing and seeding to harvesting. Their efficiency largely depends on the traction performance, which is the grip between the tires and the ground affecting fuel consumption, soil compaction, and operational efficiency (Bekker, 1969; Wong, 2010). The fundamental concepts of terramechanics were established in early seminal works by Bekker (1969) and remain a cornerstone

for understanding tire-terrain interaction, while more recent studies (Wong, 2001; Wong, 2010) have expanded and refined these models for modern agricultural applications. Tire lug design is a pivotal factor influencing traction, with parameters such as lug depth, angle, spacing, and shape significantly affecting the tire-soil interaction (Wong, 2010). Optimizing these parameters can enhance traction performance, reduce operational costs, and boost agricultural productivity.

Graduate School of Bioresources, Mie University, Japan.

*Corresponding author - email: wang@bio.mie-u.ac.jp

Received: 24 April 2025; Revised: 26 July 2025; Accepted: 13 August 2025.

Although vehicle-terrain interactions have been widely studied using empirical methods and advanced numerical simulations, there remains a need to integrate these approaches to optimize traction under varying soil conditions. This study addresses this gap by employing finite element analysis (FEA) via ANSYS and the semi-empirical Improved Tire Model by Wong and Preston-Thomas (ITM-WP). These methods are complemented by empirical data from laboratory experiments on clay soils to run the simulation models.

Previous studies provide valuable insights into traction optimization for agricultural vehicles. Alcock and Wittig (1992) developed an empirical method emphasizing soil strength and wheel torque, establishing the role of soil properties in traction performance. Maclaurin (1987) highlighted terrain-specific traction optimization through numerical simulations, stressing environmental factors in tire design. Kim *et al.* (2022) demonstrated the significance of tire contact area and lug design for traction in paddy fields, while Brennensthal *et al.* (2024) explored the interplay between lug design and terrain characteristics for tractor tires in forest conditions.

Taheri (2015) introduced the Hybrid Soft Soil Tire Model (HSSSTM), showcasing its precision in deformable terrain simulations, and Kim *et al.* (2019) identified soil moisture content as a key factor influencing dynamic traction and efficiency during plow tillage. Asaf *et al.* (2006) used discrete element methods (DEM) to analyze soil-wheel interactions, offering detailed insights into traction dynamics. Tiwari *et al.* (2010) reviewed traction prediction models, advocating for adaptability to specific soil conditions, while Sedara (2019) and Wismer (1982) contributed foundational knowledge on soil dynamics under vehicular loads. Moreland *et al.* (2011) advanced soil motion analysis techniques, and Saengprachatanarug *et al.* (2013) developed models for soil displacement and strain

distribution. Mardani and Golanbari (2024) focused on indoor analysis of soil-traction device interactions, and studies by Grujicic *et al.* (2010) and Zhou *et al.* (2020) demonstrated the efficacy of FEA in modeling soil-tire dynamics, underscoring its utility in traction optimization.

Building on these foundations, this study examines the impact of tire lug configurations on traction, motion resistance, and thrust across diverse terrains. By leveraging advanced numerical tools and integrating empirical data, it seeks to provide practical guidelines for designing efficient agricultural tires. The findings aim to enhance farming productivity by improving tire performance and reducing operational inefficiencies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Theoretical Framework and Principle

Tire performance on various soil types has been evaluated using approaches ranging from empirical methods to theoretical models (Wong, 2010). This study adopts a hybrid approach, combining the Finite Element Method (FEM) via ANSYS with the semi-empirical Improved Tire Model by Wong and Preston-Thomas (ITM-WP). Prior studies (Liu and Wong, 1996; Seta *et al.*, 2003; Wong, 2010) demonstrate strong qualitative alignment between FEM simulations and experimental data, underscoring the reliability of FEM for modeling tire-soil interactions. This research employs 3D steel tire and soil models (Fig. 1 and 2) to analyze normal and shear stresses at the tire-soil interface using ANSYS. The ITM-WP model is then applied to predict traction performance based on these stress values.

2.2. Bekker Tire-Soil Interaction Model

Bekker's tire-soil interaction model (Bekker, 1969) is a widely recognized semi-empirical method for predicting tire performance on unprepared terrain (Wong, 2010). It assumes that normal pressure at the tire's circumference is equivalent to the pressure beneath a sinkage plate at the same depth, with sinkage z_r calculated using Eq. (1) (Fig. 1).

$$z_r = \left(\frac{3W}{b_{ti}(3-n)(k_c/b + k_\phi)\sqrt{D}} \right)^{2/(2n+1)} \dots (1)$$

Where, b is the smaller dimensions of the tire contact patch, mm; b_{ti} is the tire width, mm; D is the tire diameter, mm; W is the tire load, kN and n , k_c and k_ϕ are the pressure sinkage parameters.

Fig. 1. The concept of the original model of tire-terrain interaction.

Bekker's model assumes a rigid tire operation on soft terrain, where motion resistance (R_c) results from creating a rut of width b_{ti} and depth, z_r , Eq. (7). The radial pressure σ at the tire-terrain interface is equated to the normal pressure p beneath a sinkage plate at the same depth, derived from the Bekker pressure-sinkage relationship.

$$R_c = b_{ti} \int_0^{\theta_0} \sigma r \sin\theta d\theta \dots (2)$$

$$W = b_{ti} \int_0^{\theta_0} \sigma r \cos\theta d\theta \dots (3)$$

$$\sigma r \sin\theta d\theta = pdz \dots (4)$$

$$r \cos\theta d\theta = pdx \dots (5)$$

$$p = \left(\frac{k_c}{b} + k_\phi \right) z^n = k_{eq} z^n \dots (6)$$

$$R_c = b_{ti} \int_0^{z_r} \left(\frac{k_c}{b} + k_\phi \right) z^n dz = b_{ti} \left(\frac{k_c}{b} + k_\phi \right) \left(\frac{z_r^{n+1}}{n+1} \right) \dots (7)$$

While foundational, Bekker's model has limitations, including its focus on steady-state conditions and exclusion of dynamic terrain behavior (Wong, 2010; Karpman *et al.*, 2023). These constraints necessitate advanced models like ITM-WP for more precise predictions.

2.2.1. Improved tire model by Wong and Preston-Thomas

To address Bekker's limitations, Wong and Preston-Thomas (1986) introduced the ITM-WP (Fig. 2), incorporating horizontal components of normal and shear stresses for a comprehensive analysis of tire-soil interactions. This model enhances predictions by accounting for stress and strain fields in the soil during tire movement (Wong, 2010).

Fig. 2. Conceptual diagram of the improved tire model.

Using numerical modeling via FEM (ANSYS), ITM-WP evaluates key performance metrics, including, Motion Resistance - Resistance encountered as the tire moves through soil; Thrust/Tractive Effort - Horizontal force propelling the vehicle forward; and Traction/Drawbar Pull - Pulling force critical for tasks like plowing and towing.

The ITM-WP offers a more realistic representation of tire-soil mechanics by addressing the contact patch geometry and associated stresses, enabling accurate predictions under varying conditions. This study employs ITM-WP alongside FEM simulations to provide reliable insights into tire performance, optimizing parameters like motion resistance and thrust efficiency.

2.3. Finite Element Analysis (FEA)

FEA is a computational technique that predicts the behavior of objects by employing the Finite Element Method (FEM), a mathematical approach that simplifies complex systems into smaller, manageable elements. These elements are analyzed using differential equations, which are assembled into a global system representing the entire problem domain (Reddy, 1993; Parsons, 2023). FEA interprets the FEM-generated results, enabling engineers to make informed design decisions by simulating the behavior of complex systems (Zienkiewicz and Taylor, 2000;

Zienkiewicz and Taylor, 2005; Bathe, 1996; Akin, 2010).

This method is especially valuable for analyzing tire-soil interactions, as it discretizes the continuous domain into finite elements. By applying FEM, FEA forms the backbone of simulation software, allowing for efficient validation of designs through virtual modeling (Cicconi *et al.*, 2018; Seth *et al.*, 2011; Galea Mifsud *et al.*, 2024). In this study, ANSYS software was utilized to examine interactions between six tires with varied lug spacing and four clay soil types (Table 2). This numerical approach eliminates the expense and risks associated with physical prototyping, making it indispensable in high-risk industries like aerospace and biomechanics (Alshoaibi and Fageehi, 2024; Tickoo, 2021).

2.4. ANSYS Simulation Software

ANSYS is a leading engineering simulation tool that employs FEM to predict and analyze the behavior of systems under diverse conditions. It addresses engineering challenges across industries such as aerospace, automotive, and energy (Brazil *et al.* 2023; Oden and Reddy, 2012; Madenci and Guven, 2015; Tickoo, 2021). For this study, the ANSYS Student version was used to perform numerical predictions of stresses at the tire-terrain interface. Despite its limitations in model size and computational capacity, it provided sufficient functionality for detailed

analysis. ANSYS's capabilities enabled the examination of dynamic tire-soil interactions, providing insights into how this affect traction performance.

2.4.1. Model setup and initialization

Using ANSYS Design Modeler, detailed 3D geometries of tires and soil were created. The tire model, representing a lugged tractor tire, was designed based on the specifications summarized in Table 1. It featured a width of 760 mm, diameter of 2228 mm, lug length of 510 mm, lug depth of 64 mm, and spacing of 130 mm. Five models with lug angles of 35°, 45°, 55°, 65°, and 75° were analyzed. The soil domain was modeled as a rectangular block measuring 2000 × 10000 × 2500 mm to accommodate realistic tire-soil interactions. Mechanical properties such as cohesion, friction angle, and compressibility were assigned based on experimental data to accurately simulate the behavior of four different clay soils under load.

2.4.2. Material properties representation

Accurate material representation ensures simulation reliability. The tire was modeled using structural steel, with an elastic modulus of 200 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.3, to simulate rigidity and isolate the lug angle's effect. For the soil, the Mohr-Coulomb material model was employed to describe failure and shear strength, Eq (8).

$$\tau = c + \sigma \tan(\phi) \quad \dots (8)$$

Where, τ is shear stress, kPa; c is cohesion, kPa; σ is normal stress on the shearing surface, kPa and ϕ is internal friction angle, degree. This model's simplicity and established reliability made it a practical choice for simulating soil behavior (Wong, 2010; Cook, 2007; Madenci and Guven, 2015; Tickoo, 2021).

2.4.3. Meshing

Meshing is critical in FEA to ensure accurate and reliable results. The tire model was discretized

into 52,000 elements, while the soil domain consisted of about 42,000 elements, totaling around 94,000 elements for the full model. A finer mesh was applied specifically at the tire-soil interface to capture stress distributions and contact interactions with greater precision. This meshing strategy effectively balanced computational detail with efficiency, especially considering the limitations of the ANSYS Student version used for simulations.

2.4.4. Simulation execution and boundary conditions

Simulations were performed using the ANSYS Explicit Dynamic solver to capture highly nonlinear, transient events involving large deformations typical of tire-soil interactions. Time steps were carefully configured to accurately reflect the dynamic behavior and to prevent numerical instabilities. Boundary conditions included fixing the edges of the soil domain and applying forces and displacements to the tire model to replicate real-world operational conditions. All simulations were conducted under a normal tire load of 35 kN with a forward velocity of 2.78 m/s, focusing on stress distribution and deformation within the tire-soil interface.

2.4.5. Limitations and validation

The constraints of the ANSYS Student version on model size and material representation posed challenges, as structural steel does not fully emulate real tire behavior. While simulation results provided valuable insights into performance trends, they should be considered indicative rather than definitive. Future studies should incorporate rubber material models and experimental validation to improve predictive accuracy and align findings with real-world conditions. Despite these limitations, the model demonstrated numerical stability and provided robust results, offering a foundation for optimizing lug designs tailored to specific soil conditions.

2.5. Evaluation of Tire Performance

The study utilized the Improved Tire Model (ITM) by Wong and Preston-Thomas to predict key performance metrics using stress values derived from ANSYS simulations. ITM provides a more realistic representation of tire-soil interaction compared to the classical Bekker Tire Model, enabling precise predictions of critical

parameters such as thrust, motion resistance, and traction. These metrics are vital for optimizing agricultural machinery design, enhancing operational efficiency, and reducing soil degradation. The model achieves high predictive accuracy by analyzing the distribution of normal pressure and shear stress at the tire-terrain interface, as outlined in Eq. (9) (Wong, 2010).

$$W = \frac{b_{tr}D}{2} \left[\int_0^{\theta_1} (p(\theta)\cos\theta + s(\theta)\sin\theta)d\theta + \int_0^{\theta_2} (p(\theta)\cos\theta - s(\theta)\sin\theta)d\theta \right] \quad \dots (9)$$

Where, b_{tr} is tire width, mm; D is tire diameter, mm; W is the normal tire load, kN; θ_1 and θ_2 are the entry and exit contact angles, respectively.

Motion resistance and thrust are due to the horizontal component of normal pressure and shear stress, respectively Wong (2010).

2.5.1. Prediction of tire motion resistance

The total motion resistance (R_o) encountered by a tire comprises factors like obstacle resistance (R_{ob}), internal resistance of the running gear (R_m), and the tire-terrain interaction resistance (R_t) (Bekker, 1969; Wong, 2010). Among these, the tire-terrain interaction significantly impacts performance.

Using ITM, the study focused on R_t , computed through Eq (10). This approach integrates the horizontal component of the normal pressure across the tire's contact patch, which is critical for understanding the resistance force generated as the tire moves through the terrain.

$$R_t = \frac{b_{tr}D}{2} \left[\int_0^{\theta_1} p(\theta)\sin\theta d\theta - \int_0^{\theta_2} p(\theta)\sin\theta d\theta \right] \quad \dots (10)$$

For lugged tire, $p(\theta)$ represents normal pressure on lugs and carcasses. If tire sinkage (z_r) is less

than lug height (h_l) then $p(\theta)$ corresponds to normal pressure on lug tips only.

2.5.2. Prediction of soil thrust (tractive effort or propelling force)

Thrust is limited by vehicle's mechanical capabilities and tire-terrain shearing interaction (Wong, 2010).

ITM calculates thrust (FFF) through the horizontal component of shear stress across the contact area, as shown in Eq. (11).

$$F = \frac{b_{tr}D}{2} \left[\int_0^{\theta_1} s(\theta)\cos\theta d\theta + \int_0^{\theta_2} s(\theta)\cos\theta d\theta \right] \quad \dots (11)$$

Here, $s(\theta)$ encompasses lug-terrain shearing and internal terrain shearing. For $z_r < h_l$, $s(\theta)$ corresponds to lug-terrain shearing only. ANSYS

simulations provided shear stress data, enabling accurate predictions of thrust under varying terrain conditions.

2.5.3. Determination of traction (drawbar pull)

Traction (F_d) represents the net force required for agricultural or construction tasks and is expressed

as the difference between thrust (F) and motion resistance (R_t) (Wong, 2010).

$$F_d = F - R_t \quad \dots (12)$$

This equation aids in evaluating a tractor's performance, offering insights into its suitability for specific tasks and terrains.

2.6. Development of 3D Tire and Soil Models

The 3D geometric details of the tire and soil models used in the simulations were carefully developed using ANSYS DesignModeler, a module within the ANSYS software suite, to accurately represent tire-soil interactions. Tire

models were designed with varied lug angles to examine their effects on performance metrics. Key dimensions including lug length, depth, and spacing were consistently maintained across models, while lug angles were systematically varied to evaluate their impact on traction and stress distribution. These detailed models provided a robust foundation for simulating complex tire-terrain mechanics with high fidelity.

Table 1. Key geometric parameters of the tire

Parameter	Value
Width, mm	760
Diameter, mm	2228
Lug angle, °	35°, 45°, 55°, 65°, and 75°
Lug height, mm	64
Lug spacing, mm	130

Table 2. Properties of experimental soil

Clay Soil – Sample No.	Moisture Content, % (w.b)	Cohesion, kPa	Internal friction angle, °	External friction angle, δ
1	08.6	0.38	42.6	20.9
2	27.7	1.98	28.4	15.4
3	34.2	1.78	28.4	17.8
4	54.4	0.62	11.1	9.5

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Stress Analysis at the Tire-Terrain Interface Using ANSYS

The analysis of various lug designs across different clay soil types provided valuable

insights into optimizing traction performance for agricultural vehicles. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) using ANSYS enabled the evaluation of stress distributions at the tire-terrain interface. The Mohr-Coulomb soil material model was applied to simulate clay soil

behavior under load, focusing on assessing the influence of different lug configurations and soil conditions on tire-soil interaction. The results demonstrate the significant role of lug design and soil type in influencing the mechanical response at the interface, affecting traction efficiency and soil deformation. These findings emphasize the importance of selecting appropriate lug parameters tailored to specific soil conditions to optimize performance and minimize adverse effects such as excessive soil compaction.

3.2. Performance Analysis of Lug Angle Configurations

This section evaluates the performance of various lug angles on clay soils, focusing on three critical metrics: motion resistance, thrust, and traction. The findings provide insights into optimizing tire design for agricultural and off-road applications.

3.2.1. Tire motion resistance

The relationships between lug angle (35° to 75°) and motion resistance were analyzed across four soil samples (Figs. 3 - 6). Results revealed that, Sample No. 1 exhibited the lowest resistance across all lug angles, likely due to lower soil cohesion or density, while Sample No. 3 displayed the highest peak at 45°, suggesting increased soil penetration and grip. Sample No. 2 showed relatively consistent resistance across lug angles, indicating lower sensitivity to lug design variations. The lowest motion resistance values were observed at 35°, 55° and 65° lug angles across all samples. This indicates that these lug angles minimize drag forces and soil friction, which could potentially reduce tire grip and overall tire performance.

3.2.2. Thrust

Thrust force peaked at 45° across all soil samples (Fig. 3 - 6), highlighting its effectiveness in optimizing tractive effort. Sample No. 3 recorded the highest thrust at this

angle, followed by Sample No. 4, indicating their responsiveness to lug design. In contrast, Samples No. 1 and No. 2 showed minimal variation, suggesting uniform soil properties or reduced sensitivity to lug angles. Thrust values declined beyond 45° and leveled off between 55° and 75°, as larger lug angles reduced soil engagement, leading to weaker grip. These findings reinforce the 45° lug angle as the optimal configuration for maximizing thrust across clay soils.

3.2.3. Traction

Traction trends mirrored those of thrust, with all soil samples showing a peak at the 45° lug angle (Fig 7). Sample No. 3 exhibited the highest traction, likely due to effective lug-soil interaction. Samples No. 1 and No. 2 demonstrated moderate traction increases, possibly due to higher soil stiffness reducing lug penetration. Traction force declined significantly beyond 45°, with the lowest values recorded between 55° and 75°, reflecting reduced soil engagement and diminished drawbar pull. These findings confirm the 45° lug angle as the optimal design for maximizing traction while balancing soil engagement and efficiency.

3.3. Validation of Findings

The results of this study aligns closely with Ekinici (2017), who found that a 45° lug angle provided the highest tractive efficiency in rigid wheels on hard soil. Ekinici's experimental findings corroborate the simulation-based results of this study, emphasizing the critical role of the 45° lug angle in optimizing tire performance. Despite differing methodologies, including physical tests in Ekinici's research and finite element analysis (FEA) in this study, both approaches identified the 45° lug angle as optimal for enhancing traction and efficiency. This agreement underscores the robustness and validity of the findings, reinforcing the importance of tailored lug configurations for diverse agricultural and off-road terrains.

Fig. 3. Thrust, traction and motion resistance for various lug angles on soil sample No. 1

Fig. 4. Thrust, traction and motion resistance for various lug angles on soil sample No. 2

Fig. 5. Thrust, traction and motion resistance for various lug angles on soil sample No. 3

Fig. 6. Thrust, traction and motion resistance for various lug angles on soil sample No. 4

Fig. 7. Comparing traction performance for all five lug angles on varied clay soil samples

4. CONCLUSIONS

This research used FEA in ANSYS and the Improved Tire Model by Wong and Preston-Thomas to numerically investigate the effect of lug angles on tire traction across clay soils. The study evaluated key performance metrics which were motion resistance, thrust, and traction to assess the impact of various lug configurations. The simulations employed a 3D steel tire model to replicate a rigid operating mode, paired with the Mohr-Coulomb material model to represent soil behavior. The findings consistently identified the 45° lug angle as the optimal configuration, offering the best balance

between soil engagement and tractive efficiency while maintaining moderate soil stress, making it suitable for a wide range of soil types. Beyond 45°, larger lug angles (55°-75°) reduced soil penetration, which lowered motion resistance but compromised traction. These results underscore the importance of tailoring lug configurations to specific soil conditions, providing valuable guidance for optimizing tire designs in agricultural and off-road applications. Future research should explore the performance of these lug configurations under other soil conditions, such as loamy and sandy soils, to broaden the applicability of the findings and provide a comprehensive understanding of lug

performance across diverse terrains. Additionally, experimental validation using full-scale tires under controlled field conditions is recommended to confirm simulation results and refine design guidelines further.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank JICA for scholarship support, MIE University for research resources, ANSYS developers, and Prof. Wong and Preston-Thomas for their valuable foundational tire model.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, H.A.; methodology, H.A., X.W. and T.L.; investigation, X.W. and T.W.; data curation, H.A., X.W. and J.G.; writing original draft preparation, H.A., X.W., X.W., X.W., T.W., T.L. and J.G.; writing review and editing H.A., X.W., T.W., T.L. and J.G.; supervision, X.W.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Akin, J.E. 2010. *Finite Element Analysis Concepts: via SolidWorks*. World Scientific, Singapore.
2. Alcock, R. and Wittig, V. 1992. An empirical method of predicting traction. *Journal of Terramechanics*, 29(4-5): 381–394.
3. Alshoaibi, A.M. and Fageehi, Y.A. 2024. A comparative analysis of 3D software for modeling fatigue crack growth: a review. *Applied Sciences*, 14(5): 1848.
4. Asaf, Z., Shmulevich, I. and Rubinstein, D. 2006. Predicting soil-rigid wheel performance using distinct element methods. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 49(3): 607–616.
5. Bathe, K.J. 1996. *Finite Element Procedures*. Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
6. Bekker, M.G. 1969. *Introduction to Terrain Vehicle Systems*. University of Michigan Press, Ann Arbor.
7. Brazil, V., Purdy, E. and Bajaj, K. 2023. *Simulation as an Improvement Technique*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
8. Brennenstul, M., Czarnecki, J. and Białczyk, W. 2024. Assessment of tractor tires used in forest conditions in terms of traction performance and impact on ground. *Croatian Journal of Forest Engineering*, 45(1): 97–114.
9. Cicconi, P., Landi, D. and Germani, M. 2018. An ecodesign approach for the lightweight engineering of cast iron parts. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 99: 2365–2388.
10. Cook, R.D. 2007. *Concepts and Applications of Finite Element Analysis*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken.
11. Ekinçi, Ş. 2017. Effect of lug angles of rigid wheel on the tractive performance on hard soil terrain. *Journal of Agricultural Faculty of Gaziosmanpaşa University (JAFAG)*, 34(3): 217–227.
12. Galea Mifsud, R., Muscat, G.A., Grima-Cornish, J.N., Dudek, K.K., Cardona, M.A., Attard, D., Farrugia, P.S., Gatt, R., Evans, K.E. and Grima, J.N. 2024. Auxetics and FEA: modern materials driven by modern simulation methods. *Materials*, 17(7): 1506.
13. Grujicic, M., Marvi, H., Arakere, G. and Haque, I. 2010. A finite element analysis of pneumatic-tire/sand interactions during off-road vehicle travel. *Multidiscipline Modeling in Materials and Structures*, 6(2): 284–308.
14. Karpman, E., Kövecses, J. and Teichmann, M. 2023. Terramechanics models augmented by machine learning representations. *Journal of Terramechanics*, 107: 75–89.

15. Kim, W.S., Kim, Y.J., Park, S.U., Nam, K.C. and Choi, C.H. 2019. Analysis of traction performance for an agricultural tractor according to soil moisture content during plow tillage. *2019 ASABE Annual International Meeting*, Paper No. 1900994.
 16. Kim, W.S., Kim, Y.J., Lee, N.J. and Kim, Y.S. 2022. Influence of tire contact area on the traction performance of a 67-kW agricultural tractor in a paddy field. *Journal of the ASABE*, 65(6): 1421–1432.
 17. Liu, C.H. and Wong, J.Y. 1996. Numerical simulations of tire–soil interaction based on critical state soil mechanics. *Journal of Terramechanics*, 33(5): 209–221.
 18. Maclaurin, E.B. 1987. Soil-vehicle interaction. *Journal of Terramechanics*, 24(4): 281–294.
 19. Madenci, E. and Guven, I. 2015. *The Finite Element Method and Applications in Engineering Using ANSYS®*. Springer, New York.
 20. Moreland, S. 2011. *Soil motion analysis system for examining wheel-soil shearing*. In: International Conference of the International Society for Terrain-Vehicle Systems. (Eds.) Scott Moreland, Krzysztof Skonieczny, David Wettergreen Colin Creager and Vivake Asnani. pp 361–377.
 21. Oden, J.T. and Reddy, J.N. 2012. *An Introduction to the Mathematical Theory of Finite Elements*. Dover Publications, pp 468.
 22. Parsons, C.L. 2023. *Generative design optimization of connecting rods*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Purdue University Graduate School, West Lafayette, USA.
 23. Reddy, J.N. 1993. *An Introduction to the Finite Element Method*, 2nd ed. McGraw-Hill, New York.
 24. Saengprachatanarug, K., Ueno, M., Taira, E. and Okayasu, T. 2013. Modeling of soil displacement and soil strain distribution under a traveling wheel. *Journal of Terramechanics*, 50(1): 5–16.
 25. Sedara, A.M. 2019. A review of soil dynamics in traction studies. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports*, 4(4): 1–13.
 26. Seta, E., Kamegawa, T. and Nakajima, Y. 2003. Prediction of snow/tire interaction using explicit FEM and FVM. *Tire Science and Technology*, 31(3): 173–188.
 27. Seth, A., Vance, J.M. and Oliver, J.H. 2011. Virtual reality for assembly methods prototyping: a review. *Virtual Reality*, 15: 5–20.
 28. Taheri, S. 2015. *A hybrid soft soil tire model (HSSTM) for vehicle mobility and deterministic performance analysis in terramechanics applications*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis. Virginia Tech, Blacksburg, USA.
 29. Tickoo, S. 2021. *ANSYS Workbench 2021 R1: A Tutorial Approach*. SDC Publications, Mission, KS.
 30. Tiwari, V.K., Pandey, K.P. and Pranav, P.K. 2010. A review on traction prediction equations. *Journal of Terramechanics*, 47(3): 191–199.
 31. Wismer, R.D. 1982. Soil dynamics: a review of theory and application. *SAE Transactions*, 91: 2266–2278.
 32. Wong, J.Y. 2001. *Theory of Ground Vehicles*, 3rd ed. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
 33. Wong, J.Y. 2010. *Terramechanics and Off-Road Vehicles Engineering*, 2nd ed. Elsevier Science, Amsterdam, the Netherlands.
 34. Wong, J.Y. and Preston-Thomas, J. 1986. Parametric analysis of tracked vehicle performance using an advanced computer simulation model. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part D: *Journal of Automobile Engineering*, 200(D2): 101–114.
-

35. Zhou, L., Gao, J., Li, Q. and Hu, C. 2020. Simulation study on tractive performance of off-road tire based on discrete element method. *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, 17(4): 3869–3893.
 36. Zienkiewicz, O.C. and Taylor, R.L. 2000. *The Finite Element Method: Solid Mechanics*, Vol. 2. Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford.
 37. Zienkiewicz, O.C. and Taylor, R.L. 2005. *The Finite Element Method for Solid and Structural Mechanics*. Elsevier, Amsterdam.
-